

On three-dimensional expansions of the polynomial function $f(n) = n^m$

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Abstract

In this article (points 3,4,5) we will study 3-D expansions of the polynomial function $f(n) = n^m$, for n, m natural numbers. These 3-D expansions are somewhat similar to the triangular (2-D) expansions of these functions, but here we consider here more index variables in the expansion, i.e. exactly 3 instead of 2. Additionally potential 3-dimensional expansions involve a different set of polynomial powers. In particular, only odd powers $m > 1$ one can develop in a 2-D way. In the 3-D case we can only consider powers of the form $m = 3l + 2$, for $l > 0$. The problem of the existence of triangular expansions of discrete polynomial functions was first raised by Petro Kolosov in February 2018. Triangular expansions are presented in general in the first two parts of the article. At the end (point 6), additional questions related to three dimensional expansions are presented.

1. Introduction

Triangular expansions of various discrete functions have long been known in mathematics. The most popular of these is Pascal's triangle, which expands the exponential function $f(n) = 2^n$. This triangle $T(n, k)$ is equal to $\binom{n}{k}$, because $\sum_{k=0}^n T(n, k) = 2^n$. The problem of the existence of a triangular expansion for the polynomial function $f(n) = n^m$ was first considered by Petro Kolosov in his mathematical works. He found such an expansion for the n^3 polynomial. The exact formula of this triangle is

$$T(n, k) = 6k(n - k) + 1, \text{ where } 1 \leq k \leq n.$$

In February 2018 he posted a question whether there are similar expansions for higher powers of n^m polynomials. In March 2018 I presented a partial answer to this question in [3]. In particular I found patterns of triangles expanding functions n^5 and n^7 . An example triangle for the fifth power is

$$T(n, k) = 30[k(n - k)]^2 + 1, \text{ where } 1 \leq k \leq n.$$

At the same time, in [3] a hypothesis was put forward about the existence of triangular expansions of polynomial functions $f(n) = n^m$ where m is odd and about the general form of these expansions. A few weeks later, this hypothesis was confirmed by Dr Max Alekseyev from George Washington University. In particular, during a discussion on a mathematical forum on the internet, he presented in [4] a recursive algorithm for calculating the coefficients of triangular expansion for a given power of an odd n^m polynomial. In April 2018 I presented in [5] a detailed description of the method I used to find the triangles presented earlier in [3]. For a given power $m = 2l + 1$ the triangle is a polynomial of degree l , where the coefficients are rational numbers and the variable is the expression $k(n - k)$. Some time later, Petro Kolosov in [1] presented relationship between triangular expansions and binomial theorem.

Generally, triangles are two-dimensional figures, and in our discrete expansions the value of a given $T(n, k)$ depends on 2 changing indexes : n and k . In this way we can treat our triangles as two dimensional (2-D) expansions.

2. Two-dimensional expansions

Theorem 1.

For every odd power $m = 2l + 1$ (for $l > 0$) there exist rational coefficients $A_{l,i}$ so that:

$$n^{2l+1} = \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{i=0}^l A_{l,i} [k(n-k)]^i$$

For a given $m = 2l + 1$ the set of coefficients $A_{l,i}$ for $0 \leq i \leq l$ describe the triangular (2-D) expansion of polynomial function $f(n) = n^m$.

The proof of theorem 1 can be found in [1].

For example for the polynomial n^3 we have the following expansion coefficients:

$$A_{1,1} = 6, A_{1,0} = 1.$$

For the polynomial n^5 we have:

$$A_{2,2} = 30, A_{2,1} = 0, A_{2,0} = 1.$$

Below are 2-D expansions for the first 5 odd powers m of the polynomial n^m :

1. $m = 3$: $n^3 = \sum_{k=1}^n 6k(n-k) + 1$
2. $m = 5$: $n^5 = \sum_{k=1}^n 30[k(n-k)]^2 + 1$
3. $m = 7$: $n^7 = \sum_{k=1}^n 140[k(n-k)]^3 - 14k(n-k) + 1$
4. $m = 9$: $n^9 = \sum_{k=1}^n 630[k(n-k)]^4 - 120k(n-k) + 1$
5. $m = 11$: $n^{11} = \sum_{k=1}^n 2772[k(n-k)]^5 + 660[k(n-k)]^2 - 1386k(n-k) + 1$

Theorem 2.

For a given $m = 2l + 1$ the coefficients $A_{l,i}$ from theorem 1 can be computed recursively as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{l,i} &:= \binom{2i}{i} (2i + 1) && \text{for } i = l \\ A_{l,i} &:= \binom{2i}{i} (2i + 1) \sum_{d=2i+1}^l A_{l,d} \binom{d}{2i+1} \frac{(-1)^{d-1}}{d-i} B_{2d-2i} && \text{for } 0 \leq i < l \\ A_{l,i} &:= 0 && \text{for } i < 0 \text{ or } i > l \end{aligned}$$

where B_t are known as Bernoulli numbers

The proof of theorem 2 and more features of 2-D expansions can be found in [1] and the definition of Bernoulli numbers in [2].

3. Three-dimensional expansions

3.1. Idea

In the case of two dimensions, the expression in the expansion is a polynomial whose variable is $k(n-k)$. For three dimensions we add an additional index j and then variable has the form $jk[n-(j+k)]$. In 2-D expansions, the parameter k of the variable satisfies the condition: $0 < k \leq n$. In 3 dimensions the condition for the parameters j, k is similar: $0 < j+k \leq n$. We can see that $\sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} jk[n-(j+k)]$ is a fifth degree polynomial of n . This means that the minimum polynomial power for potential 3-D expansions cannot be less than 5. If we take successive powers of the expression $jk(n-j-k)$, the degree of the polynomial of n for the corresponding sum will increase by 3 each time. Because of that, the m powers of the polynomial n^m , which we could potentially expand in three dimensions, must be $m = 3l + 2$, where $1 \leq l$. The calculations performed for the 5-th power showed that there is no expansion of n^5 in a form similar to the 2-D case i.e. $Ajk(n-j-k) + C$, where the coefficient A and C would be constant numbers. For a three-dimensional expansion to be possible in this case, C must be a degree 3 polynomial with variable n . For expansions of polynomials higher than n^5 , some of the coefficients in the expressions $[jk(n-j-k)]^i$ must be also low degree polynomials of variable n .

Now let's think about now how many sum terms there are in a potential 3-D expansion. In the case of 2-D, there are exactly n expressions (sum over k where $0 < k \leq n$), which is also equal to $\binom{n+1}{1} - 1$.

For 3 dimensions we can easily prove that number of pairs (j, k) where $0 < j+k \leq n$ is equal to $\binom{n+2}{2} - 1$ (we do not consider only the pair where both $j = 0$ and $k = 0$). We can further note that $\binom{n+2}{2} - 1$ is equal to $\frac{n^2+3n}{2}$.

3.2. Definition and examples

Three-dimensional expansion of the polynomial function $f(n) = n^m$ where $m = 3l + 2$ (for $1 \leq l$) is a set of polynomials of variable n with rational coefficients $\{C_{l,i}(n)\}_{i=0,1,\dots,l}$ in the following form:

$$C_{l,i}(n) = \begin{cases} C_{l,i,0} & \text{for } i = l \\ C_{l,i,2}n^2 + C_{l,i,1}n + C_{l,i,0} & \text{for } 0 < i < l \\ C_{l,i,3}n^3 + C_{l,i,2}n^2 + C_{l,i,1}n + C_{l,i,0} & \text{for } i = 0 \end{cases}$$

where there is satisfied for every n natural the following equation:

$$n^{3l+2} = \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} \sum_{i=0}^l C_{l,i}(n) j^i k^i (n-j-k)^i$$

Example 1.

When the power of $m = 5$, the 3-D expansion is:

$$n^5 = \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} C_{1,1}(n)jk(n-j-k) + C_{1,0}(n)$$

or in more exact form:

$$n^5 = \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} C_{1,1,0}jk(n-j-k) + C_{1,0,3}n^3 + C_{1,0,2}n^2 + C_{1,0,1}n + C_{1,0,0}$$

Example 2.

When the power of $m = 8$, the formula of 3-D expansion is:

$$n^8 = \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} C_{2,2}(n)j^2k^2(n-j-k)^2 + C_{2,1}(n)jk(n-j-k) + C_{2,0}(n)$$

or in more exact form:

$$n^8 = \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} \left(C_{2,2,0}j^2k^2(n-j-k)^2 + (C_{2,1,2}n^2 + C_{2,1,1}n + C_{2,1,0})jk(n-j-k) \right. \\ \left. + C_{2,0,3}n^3 + C_{2,0,2}n^2 + C_{2,0,1}n + C_{2,0,0} \right)$$

In the next sections of the article the exact 3-D expansions of the functions: n^5 , n^8 and n^{11} and the method of obtaining them are presented.

3.3. The expansions for functions $f(n) = n^5$, $f(n) = n^8$ and $f(n) = n^{11}$

3.3.1. The case of $f(n) = n^5$

$$n^5 = \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} \left(243jk(n-j-k) - \frac{41}{20}n^3 + \frac{123}{20}n^2 + \frac{9}{5}n - \frac{27}{5} \right)$$

3.3.2. The case of $f(n) = n^8$

$$n^8 = \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} \left(5040j^2k^2(n-j-k)^2 - 1521jk(n-j-k) + \frac{507}{20}n^3 - \frac{681}{20}n^2 \right. \\ \left. - \frac{123}{5}n + \frac{169}{5} \right)$$

This means in this case that the polynomial $C_{2,1}(n)$ is a constant number i.e. $C_{2,1,2} = 0$, $C_{2,1,1} = 0$, $C_{2,1,0} = -1521$.

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3.3.3. The case of $f(n) = n^{11}$

$$n^{11} = \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} \left(184800j^3k^3(n-j-k)^3 + (-3960n^2 + 27987)jk(n-j-k) - \frac{2729}{20}n^3 \right) + \frac{8187}{20}n^2 + \frac{681}{5}n - \frac{2043}{5}$$

This means in this case that the polynomial $C_{3,2}(n) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 0$ and the coefficient $C_{3,1,1}$ of the polynomial $C_{3,1}(n)$ is equal to 0.

3.4. A method for finding 3-D expansions

In our method of finding 3-D expansions, the expansion expression first needs to be transformed into a polynomial of the variable n , where the coefficients of the polynomial depend on the desired 3-D expansion coefficients C_{l,i_0,i_1} . Secondly, we compare the values of the individual coefficients for a given power of n so as to obtain the polynomial n^{3l+2} . As a result of this comparison, we obtain a system of linear equations in which the unknowns are C_{l,i_0,i_1} . If we solve the system of equations, we get the three-dimensional expansion coefficients for a given function $f(n) = n^{3l+2}$. This method requires knowing the expected form of the expansion expression. In other words, we need to know which coefficients C_{l,i_0,i_1} are likely to be non-zero. We can predict this when we know what in general polynomial of n is $\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} [jk(n-j-k)]^l$.

In particular, we need to know here what unit polynomials n^i other than n^{3l+2} occur in the above expression. We will further call these polynomials in the form n^i as units.

For this purpose, we use the following identities in our method:

$$\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} jk(n-j-k) = \frac{n^5 - 5n^3 + 4n}{120} \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} j^2k^2(n-j-k)^2 = \frac{n^8 - 21n^4 + 20n^2}{5040} \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} j^3k^3(n-j-k)^3 = \frac{n^{11} + 33n^7 - 330n^5 + 616n^3 - 320n}{184800} \quad (3)$$

The above identities can be obtained by applying appropriate transformations and formulas for sums of powers of successive natural numbers.

Let's derive for example formula (1) :

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} jk(n-j-k) &= \sum_{j=0}^n j \sum_{k=0}^{n-j} k(n-j-k) = \sum_{j=0}^n j \left((n-j) \sum_{k=0}^{n-j} k - \sum_{k=0}^{n-j} k^2 \right) = \\
\sum_{j=0}^n j \left((n-j) \frac{(n-j)(n-j+1)}{2} - \frac{2(n-j)^3 + 3(n-j)^2 + n-j}{6} \right) &= \\
\sum_{j=0}^n j \left(\frac{(n-j)^3 + (n-j)^2}{2} - \frac{2(n-j)^3 + 3(n-j)^2 + n-j}{6} \right) &= \\
\sum_{j=0}^n j \left(\frac{(n-j)^3 - (n-j)}{6} \right) = \sum_{j=0}^n j \left(\frac{n^3 - 3n^2j + 3nj^2 - j^3 - n + j}{6} \right) &= \\
\sum_{j=0}^n \left(\frac{-j^4 + 3nj^3 + (-3n^2 + 1)j^2 + (n^3 - n)j}{6} \right) &= \\
-\frac{1}{6} \sum_{j=0}^n j^4 + \frac{1}{2} n \sum_{j=0}^n j^3 + \frac{(-3n^2 + 1)}{6} \sum_{j=0}^n j^2 + \frac{(n^3 - n)}{6} \sum_{j=0}^n j &= \\
-\frac{1}{6} \left(\frac{6n^5 + 15n^4 + 10n^3 - n}{30} \right) + \frac{1}{2} n \left(\frac{n^4 + 2n^3 + n^2}{4} \right) + \\
\frac{(-3n^2 + 1)}{6} \left(\frac{2n^3 + 3n^2 + n}{6} \right) + \frac{(n^3 - n)}{6} \left(\frac{n^2 + n}{2} \right) &= \\
\frac{-6n^5 - 15n^4 - 10n^3 + n}{180} + \frac{n^5 + 2n^4 + n^3}{8} + \\
\frac{-6n^5 - 9n^4 - n^3 + 3n^2 + n}{36} + \frac{n^5 + n^4 - n^3 - n^2}{12} &= \\
\frac{3n^5 - 15n^3 + 12n}{360} = \frac{n^5 - 5n^3 + 4n}{120}
\end{aligned}$$

3.4.1. Finding the expansion $f(n) = n^5$

For the smallest polynomial n^5 , the 3D-expansion expression is expected in the only possible way, since we can hardly consider the situation that some expansion coefficients can be equal to 0. So that in this case our 3-D expansion is:

$$\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} C_{1,1,0} jk(n-j-k) + C_{1,0,3} n^3 + C_{1,0,2} n^2 + C_{1,0,1} n + C_{1,0,0}$$

where the coefficients $\{C_{1,1,0}, C_{1,0,3}, C_{1,0,2}, C_{1,0,1}, C_{1,0,0}\}$ are the unknowns sought.

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Rearranging the above equation we get :

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} C_{1,1,0}jk(n-j-k) + \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} C_{1,0,3}n^3 + C_{1,0,2}n^2 + C_{1,0,1}n + C_{1,0,0} = \\
& C_{1,1,0} \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} k(n-j-k) + (C_{1,0,3}n^3 + C_{1,0,2}n^2 + C_{1,0,1}n + C_{1,0,0}) \left(\frac{n^2 + 3n}{2} \right) = \\
& C_{1,1,0} \left(\frac{n^5 - 5n^3 + 4n}{120} \right) + \frac{C_{1,0,3}}{2}n^5 + \frac{(3C_{1,0,3} + C_{1,0,2})n^4}{2} + \frac{(3C_{1,0,2} + C_{1,0,1})n^3}{2} + \\
& \frac{(3C_{1,0,1} + C_{1,0,0})n^2}{2} + \frac{3C_{1,0,0}n}{2} = \\
& \frac{C_{1,1,0}n^5}{120} - \frac{C_{1,1,0}n^3}{24} + \frac{C_{1,1,0}n}{30} + \frac{C_{1,0,3}n^5}{2} + \frac{(3C_{1,0,3} + C_{1,0,2})n^4}{2} + \\
& \frac{(3C_{1,0,2} + C_{1,0,1})n^3}{2} + \frac{(3C_{1,0,1} + C_{1,0,0})n^2}{2} + \frac{3C_{1,0,0}n}{2} = \\
& \frac{(C_{1,1,0} + 60C_{1,0,3})n^5}{120} + \frac{(3C_{1,0,3} + C_{1,0,2})n^4}{2} + \frac{(-C_{1,1,0} + 36C_{1,0,2} + 12C_{1,0,1})n^3}{24} + \\
& \frac{(3C_{1,0,1} + C_{1,0,0})n^2}{2} + \frac{(C_{1,1,0} + 45C_{1,0,0})n}{30}.
\end{aligned}$$

The above polynomial of n is equal to n^5 only if the coefficients $\{C_{1,1,0}, C_{1,0,3}, C_{1,0,2}, C_{1,0,1}, C_{1,0,0}\}$ are a solution to the following system of 5 linear equations:

$$\begin{cases}
C_{1,1,0} + 60C_{1,0,3} & = 120 \\
3C_{1,0,3} + C_{1,0,2} & = 0 \\
C_{1,1,0} + 36C_{1,0,2} + 12C_{1,0,1} & = 0 \\
3C_{1,0,1} + C_{1,0,0} & = 0 \\
C_{1,1,0} + 45C_{1,0,0} & = 0
\end{cases}$$

If we solve the system, the coefficients must be: $C_{1,1,0} = 243$, $C_{1,0,3} = \frac{-41}{20}$, $C_{1,0,2} = \frac{123}{20}$, $C_{1,0,1} = \frac{9}{5}$, $C_{1,0,0} = \frac{-27}{5}$.

3.4.2. Finding the expansion $f(n) = n^8$

First, we must note that the polynomial form of the expression $\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} j^2k^2(n-j-k)^2$ contains

only units n^8 , n^4 and n^2 . For this reason, the polynomial $C_{2,1}(n)$ must be a constant number.

Otherwise we would introduce a new unit n^7 or n^6 into the 3D-expansion expression, which we could not eliminate later. As a final result, our expected form of 3-D expansion in this case is:

$$\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} (C_{2,2,0}j^2k^2(n-j-k)^2 + C_{2,1,0}jk(n-j-k) + C_{2,0,3}n^3 + C_{2,0,2}n^2 + C_{2,0,1}n + C_{2,0,0})$$

where $\{C_{2,2,0}, C_{2,1,0}, C_{2,0,3}, C_{2,0,2}, C_{2,0,1}, C_{2,0,0}\}$ are searched unknowns.

Rearranging the above equation, we get :

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} C_{2,2,0} j^2 k^2 (n-j-k)^2 + C_{2,1,0} j k (n-j-k) + \\
& \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} C_{2,0,3} n^3 + C_{2,0,2} n^2 + C_{2,0,1} n + C_{2,0,0} = \\
& C_{2,2,0} \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} j^2 k^2 (n-j-k)^2 + C_{2,1,0} \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} k(n-j-k) + \\
& (C_{2,0,3} n^3 + C_{2,0,2} n^2 + C_{2,0,1} n + C_{2,0,0}) \left(\frac{n^2 + 3n}{2} \right) = \\
& C_{2,2,0} \left(\frac{n^8 - 21n^4 + 20n^2}{5040} \right) + C_{2,1,0} \left(\frac{n^5 - 5n^3 + 4n}{120} \right) + \frac{C_{2,0,3}}{2} n^5 + \frac{(3C_{2,0,3} + C_{2,0,2})n^4}{2} + \\
& \frac{(3C_{2,0,2} + C_{2,0,1})n^3}{2} + \frac{(3C_{2,0,1} + C_{2,0,0})n^2}{2} + \frac{3C_{2,0,0}n}{2} = \\
& \frac{C_{2,2,0}n^8}{5040} - \frac{C_{2,2,0}n^4}{240} + \frac{C_{2,2,0}n^2}{252} + \frac{C_{2,1,0}n^5}{120} - \frac{C_{2,1,0}n^3}{24} + \frac{C_{2,1,0}n}{30} + \frac{C_{2,0,3}n^5}{2} + \frac{(3C_{2,0,3} + C_{2,0,2})n^4}{2} + \\
& \frac{(3C_{2,0,2} + C_{2,0,1})n^3}{2} + \frac{(3C_{2,0,1} + C_{2,0,0})n^2}{2} + \frac{3C_{2,0,0}n}{2} = \\
& \frac{C_{2,2,0}n^8}{5040} + \frac{(C_{2,1,0} + 60C_{2,0,3})n^5}{120} + \frac{(-C_{2,2,0} + 360C_{2,0,3} + 120C_{2,0,2})n^4}{240} + \\
& \frac{(-C_{2,1,0} + 36C_{2,0,2} + 12C_{2,0,1})n^3}{24} + \frac{(C_{2,2,0} + 378C_{2,0,1} + 126C_{2,0,0})n^2}{252} + \frac{(C_{2,1,0} + 45C_{2,0,0})n}{30}
\end{aligned}$$

The above polynomial of n is equal n^8 only if the coefficients $\{C_{2,2,0}, C_{2,1,0}, C_{2,0,3}, C_{2,0,2}, C_{2,0,1}, C_{2,0,0}\}$ are a solution of the following system of 6 linear equations:

$$\begin{cases}
C_{2,2,0} & = 5040 \\
C_{2,1,0} + 60C_{2,0,3} & = 0 \\
-C_{2,2,0} + 360C_{2,0,3} + 120C_{2,0,2} & = 0 \\
-C_{2,1,0} + 36C_{2,0,2} + 12C_{2,0,1} & = 0 \\
C_{2,2,0} + 378C_{2,0,1} + 126C_{2,0,0} & = 0 \\
C_{2,1,0} + 45C_{2,0,0} & = 0
\end{cases}$$

As in the previous case the system has only one solution: $C_{2,2,0} = 5040$, $C_{2,1,0} = -1521$, $C_{2,0,3} = \frac{507}{20}$, $C_{2,0,2} = \frac{-681}{20}$, $C_{2,0,1} = \frac{-123}{5}$, $C_{2,0,0} = \frac{169}{5}$.

3.4.3. Finding the expansion $f(n) = n^{11}$

As in the previous case, we first study the polynomial form of $\sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^3 k^3 (n-j-k)^3$. There are units: n^{11}, n^7, n^5, n^3, n . For this reason, the polynomial $C_{3,2}(n)$ must by definition be equal to 0. Otherwise, we would introduce a new unit into the 3D-expansion expression, i.e. n^{10} or n^9 or n^8 , which we could not later eliminate. On the other hand, to eliminate n^7 , the polynomial $C_{3,1}(n)$ must be of second degree, i.e. $C_{3,1,2} \neq 0$. In addition, the coefficient $C_{3,1,1}$ in this polynomial must be equal to 0. Otherwise we would introduce a new unit, i.e. n^6 , that we could not eliminate later. As a final result, our expected form of 3-D expansion in this case is:

$$\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} \left(C_{3,3,0} j^3 k^3 (n-j-k)^3 + (C_{3,1,2} n^2 + C_{3,1,0}) jk(n-j-k) \right. \\ \left. + C_{3,0,3} n^3 + C_{3,0,2} n^2 + C_{3,0,1} n + C_{3,0,0} \right)$$

where coefficients $\{C_{3,3,0}, C_{3,1,2}, C_{3,1,0}, C_{3,0,3}, C_{3,0,2}, C_{3,0,1}, C_{3,0,0}\}$ are searched unknowns.

Rearranging the above expression, we get :

$$\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} C_{3,3,0} j^3 k^3 (n-j-k)^3 + (C_{3,1,2} n^2 + C_{3,1,0}) jk(n-j-k) + \\ \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} C_{3,0,3} n^3 + C_{3,0,2} n^2 + C_{3,0,1} n + C_{3,0,0} =$$

$$C_{3,3,0} \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} (jk(n-j-k))^3 + (C_{3,1,2} n^2 + C_{3,1,0}) \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} jk(n-j-k) + \\ (C_{3,0,3} n^3 + C_{3,0,2} n^2 + C_{3,0,1} n + C_{3,0,0}) \left(\frac{n^2 + 3n}{2} \right) =$$

$$C_{3,3,0} \left(\frac{n^{11} + 33n^7 - 330n^5 + 616n^3 - 320n}{184800} \right) + (C_{3,1,2} n^2 + C_{3,1,0}) \left(\frac{n^5 - 5n^3 + 4n}{120} \right) + \\ \frac{C_{3,0,3}}{2} n^5 + \frac{(3C_{3,0,3} + C_{3,0,2})n^4}{2} + \frac{(3C_{3,0,2} + C_{3,0,1})n^3}{2} + \frac{(3C_{3,0,1} + C_{3,0,0})n^2}{2} + \frac{3C_{3,0,0}n}{2} = \\ \frac{C_{3,3,0} n^{11}}{184800} + \frac{(3C_{3,3,0} + 140C_{3,1,2})n^7}{16800} + \frac{(-3C_{3,3,0} - 70C_{3,1,2} + 14C_{3,1,0} + 840C_{3,0,3})n^5}{1680} + \\ \frac{(3C_{3,0,3} + C_{3,0,2})n^4}{2} + \frac{(2C_{3,3,0} + 20C_{3,1,2} - 25C_{3,1,0} + 900C_{3,0,2} + 300C_{3,0,1})n^3}{600} + \\ \frac{(3C_{3,0,1} + C_{3,0,0})n^2}{2} + \frac{(-4C_{3,3,0} + 77C_{3,1,0} + 3465C_{3,0,0})n}{2310}$$

The above polynomial is equal to n^{11} only than the coefficients $\{C_{3,3,0}, C_{3,1,2}, C_{3,1,0}, C_{3,0,3}, C_{3,0,2}, C_{3,0,1}, C_{3,0,0}\}$ are a solution the following system of 7 linear equations:

$$\begin{cases} C_{3,3,0} & = 184800 \\ 3C_{3,3,0} + 140C_{3,1,2} & = 0 \\ -3C_{3,3,0} - 70C_{3,1,2} + 14C_{3,1,0} + 840C_{3,0,3} & = 0 \\ 3C_{3,0,3} + C_{3,0,2} & = 0 \\ 2C_{3,3,0} + 20C_{3,1,2} - 25C_{3,1,0} + 900C_{3,0,2} + 300C_{3,0,1} & = 0 \\ 3C_{3,0,1} + C_{3,0,0} & = 0 \\ -4C_{3,3,0} + 77C_{3,1,0} + 3465C_{3,0,0} & = 0 \end{cases}$$

The above system has only one solution: $C_{3,3,0} = 184800$, $C_{3,1,2} = -3960$, $C_{3,1,0} = 27987$, $C_{3,0,3} = -\frac{2729}{20}$, $C_{3,0,2} = \frac{8187}{20}$, $C_{3,0,1} = \frac{681}{5}$, $C_{3,0,0} = -\frac{2043}{5}$.

4. Properties of three-dimensional expansions

Let's assume that $\{C_{l,i}(n)\}_{i=0,1,\dots,l}$ is a three-dimensional expansion of the polynomial function $f(n) = n^{3l+2}$ according to definition 3.2 then:

$$\mathbf{4.1.} \quad C_{l,l}(n) = C_{l,l,0} = \begin{cases} (2l+1) \binom{2l}{l} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \frac{\binom{2l+1}{k}}{k+l+1} (-1)^k \right)^{-1} & \text{for } l > 1 \\ 3^5 & \text{for } l = 1 \end{cases}$$

4.2. If $l > 2$ and $i < l$ and $C_{l,i}(n) \neq 0$ then:

$$C_{l,i}(n) = \begin{cases} C_{l,i,2}n^2 + C_{l,i,0} & \text{for } i > 1 \text{ and } l \equiv i \pmod{2} \\ C_{l,i,1}n & \text{for } i > 1 \text{ and } l \not\equiv i \pmod{2} \\ C_{l,i,2}n^2 + C_{l,i,0} & \text{for } i = 1 \text{ and } l \text{ odd} \\ C_{l,i,1}n + C_{l,i,0} & \text{for } i = 1 \text{ and } l \text{ even} \\ C_{l,i,3}n^3 + C_{l,i,2}n^2 + C_{l,i,1}n + C_{l,i,0} & \text{for } i = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\mathbf{4.3.} \quad C_{l,0}(1) = 1, \quad C_{l,0}(2) = \frac{1}{5} 2^{3l+2}$$

$$\mathbf{4.4.} \quad C_{l,l}(3) + C_{l,l-1}(3) + \dots + C_{l,1}(3) + 9 C_{l,0}(3) = 3^{3l+2}$$

Properties **4.3** and **4.4** can be easy proven directly by use of the definition of 3-D expansion of $f(n) = n^{3l+2}$.

To proof properties **4.1** and **4.2**, we first need to find the polynomial form of the expression $\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} j^l k^l (n-j-k)^l$ for $l \geq 1$. Second, we need to determine what exactly units n^i exist in this form for a given l .

On three-dimensional expansions of the polynomial function $f(n) = n^m$

For this purpose, we will use the following formula:

$$\sum_{k=1}^l k^l (n-k)^l = \frac{n^{2l+1}}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}} + 2(-1)^l \sum_{k=0}^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} n^{l-k}$$

where B_t are Bernoulli numbers

The proof of the above formula can be found in [1].

Rearranging the main expression, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} j^l k^l (n-j-k)^l &= \sum_{j=0}^n \left(j^l \sum_{k=1}^{n-j} k^l (n-j-k)^l \right) = \\ \sum_{j=0}^n \left(j^l \left(\frac{(n-j)^{2l+1}}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}} + 2(-1)^l \sum_{k=0}^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} (n-j)^{l-k} \right) \right) &= \\ \sum_{j=0}^n \left(\frac{j^l (n-j)^{2l+1}}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}} + 2(-1)^l \sum_{k=0}^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} j^l (n-j)^{l-k} \right) &= \\ \sum_{j=0}^n \frac{j^l (n-j)^{2l+1}}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}} + 2(-1)^l \sum_{j=0}^n \sum_{k=0}^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} j^l (n-j)^{l-k} &= P_1(n) + P_2(n), \\ \text{where } P_1(n) = \sum_{j=0}^n \frac{j^l (n-j)^{2l+1}}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}}, \quad P_2(n) = 2(-1)^l \sum_{j=0}^n \sum_{k=0}^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} j^l (n-j)^{l-k} \end{aligned}$$

Due to the complexity of the formulas, for greater clarity, we first find the polynomial form of the expression $P_1(n)$, and then the analogous form of the expression $P_2(n)$. For this purpose, we will use the formula for the sum of powers of consecutive natural numbers:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n j^p = \frac{1}{p+1} \sum_{i=0}^p n^{p+1-i} \binom{p+1}{i} B_i$$

where B_i are Bernoulli numbers

Coming back to the expression $P_1(n)$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} P_1(n) &= \sum_{j=0}^n \frac{j^l (n-j)^{2l+1}}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}} = \left(\frac{1}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^n \sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k n^{2l+1-k} j^{k+l} = \\ \left((2l+1) \binom{2l}{l} \right)^{-1} \sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k n^{2l+1-k} \sum_{j=0}^n j^{k+l} &= \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left((2l+1) \binom{2l}{l} \right)^{-1} \sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k n^{2l+1-k} \frac{1}{k+l+1} \sum_{i=0}^{k+l} n^{k+l+1-i} \binom{k+l+1}{i} B_i = \\
 & \left((2l+1) \binom{2l}{l} \right)^{-1} \sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{k+l+1} \sum_{i=0}^{k+l} n^{3l+2-i} \binom{k+l+1}{i} B_i = \\
 & \left((2l+1) \binom{2l}{l} \right)^{-1} \sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \sum_{i=0}^{k+l} \binom{2l+1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{k+l+1} \binom{k+l+1}{i} B_i n^{3l+2-i} = \\
 & \frac{1}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}} \left(\sum_{i=0}^l B_i \sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{k+l+1} \binom{k+l+1}{i} n^{3l+2-i} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \sum_{i=l+1}^{3l+1} B_i \sum_{k=i-l}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{k+l+1} \binom{k+l+1}{i} n^{3l+2-i} \right) = \\
 & \frac{1}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}} \left(\sum_{i=0}^l B_i \sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k \frac{\binom{k+l+1}{i}}{k+l+1} n^{3l+2-i} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \sum_{i=l+1}^{3l+1} B_i \sum_{k=i-l}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k \frac{\binom{k+l+1}{i}}{k+l+1} n^{3l+2-i} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

The above expression is a polynomial of n of degree $3l+2$. We must note to that this polynomial obviously contains the unit n^{3l+2} , but not the units : $n^{3l+1}, n^{3l}, n^{3l-1}, \dots, n^{2l+2}$. In other words, the corresponding coefficients for the listed units less than n^{3l+2} are equal to 0. To proof this, we will use the following identity related with binomial coefficients:

$$\sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} (-1)^k (a_m k^m + a_{m-1} k^{m-1} + \dots + a_1 k + a_0) = (-1)^m m! a_m \quad (4)$$

The proof of the above identity can be found in [2].

From the identity (4) follows the next one, which we will use directly for our problem with no-existent units in the polynomial $P_1(n)$. In particular, if $A(k)$ is a polynomial of k of degree less than m then:

$$\sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} (-1)^k A(k) = 0 \quad (5)$$

Identity (5) is an individual case of identity (4) exactly when $a_m = 0$.

Returning to the polynomial $P_1(n)$, the corresponding coefficient for n^{3l+2-i} , where $1 \leq i \leq l$ is:

$$B_i \sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k \frac{\binom{k+l+1}{i}}{k+l+1} \quad (6)$$

If we assume that l and i are constants and $1 \leq i \leq l$, then $\frac{\binom{k+l+1}{i}}{k+l+1}$ is a polynomial of k of degree $i - 1$. Given the identity (5), we get that the coefficient (6) is equal to 0, for $1 \leq i \leq l$. Additionally, we note that $B_0 = 1$.

Thus, in the final result we can present the polynomial $P_1(n)$ in the form:

$$\frac{1}{(2l+1)\binom{2l}{l}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \frac{\binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k}{k+l+1} n^{3l+2} + \sum_{i=l+1}^{3l+1} B_i \sum_{k=i-l}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k \frac{\binom{k+l+1}{i}}{k+l+1} n^{3l+2-i} \right)$$

Now, let's go to the expression $P_2(n)$:

$$\begin{aligned} P_2(n) &= 2(-1)^l \sum_{j=0}^n \sum_{k=0}^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} j^l (n-j)^{l-k} = \\ &= 2(-1)^l \sum_{j=0}^n \sum_{k=0}^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{m=0}^{l-k} \binom{l-k}{m} (-1)^m n^{l-k-m} j^{l+m} = \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^l 2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{m=0}^{l-k} \binom{l-k}{m} (-1)^m n^{l-k-m} \sum_{j=0}^n j^{l+m} = \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^l 2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{m=0}^{l-k} \binom{l-k}{m} (-1)^m n^{l-k-m} \frac{1}{l+m+1} \sum_{i=0}^{l+m} n^{l+m+1-i} \binom{l+m+1}{i} B_i = \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^l 2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{m=0}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m}^{l+m}}{l+m+1} \sum_{i=0}^{l+m} n^{2l+1-k-i} \binom{l+m+1}{i} B_i = \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^l 2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{m=0}^{l-k} \sum_{i=0}^{l+m} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m}}{l+m+1} \binom{l+m+1}{i} B_i n^{2l+1-k-i} = \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^l 2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \left(\sum_{i=0}^l \sum_{m=0}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m}}{l+m+1} \binom{l+m+1}{i} B_i n^{2l+1-k-i} + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \sum_{i=l+1}^{2l-k} \sum_{m=i-l}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m}}{l+m+1} \binom{l+m+1}{i} B_i n^{2l+1-k-i} \right) = \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^l 2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} \frac{B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \left(\sum_{i=0}^{l-k} \sum_{m=0}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m}}{l+m+1} \binom{l+m+1}{i} B_i n^{2l+1-k-i} + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \sum_{i=l-k+1}^l \sum_{m=0}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m}}{l+m+1} \binom{l+m+1}{i} B_i n^{2l+1-k-i} + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \sum_{i=l+1}^{2l-k} \sum_{m=i-l}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m}}{l+m+1} \binom{l+m+1}{i} B_i n^{2l+1-k-i} \right) = \end{aligned}$$

We can simplify the first item of the above sum in brackets using the identity (5). In particular, :

$$\sum_{m=0}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m}}{l+m+1} \binom{l+m+1}{i} = 0, \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, l-k$$

Thereby we can present our expression $P_2(n)$ in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^l \frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{m=0}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m}}{l+m+1} n^{2l+1-k} + \\ & \sum_{k=0}^l \frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{i=l-k+1}^l \sum_{m=0}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m} \binom{l+m+1}{i}}{l+m+1} B_i n^{2l+1-(k+i)} + \\ & \sum_{k=0}^l \frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{i=l+1}^{2l-k} \sum_{m=i-l}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m} \binom{l+m+1}{i}}{l+m+1} B_i n^{2l+1-(k+i)} \end{aligned}$$

If we change indexes in powers of unit polynomials n^l , we can present $P_2(n)$ in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=0}^l \left(\frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{i} B_{l+i+1}}{l+i+1} \sum_{m=0}^{l-i} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-i}{m}}{l+m+1} \right) n^{2l+1-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=l+1}^{2l} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{i-l-1} \frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{m=i-k-l}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m} \binom{l+m+1}{i-k}}{l+m+1} B_{i-k} + \right. \\ & \left. \sum_{k=i-l}^l \frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{m=0}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m} \binom{l+m+1}{i-k}}{l+m+1} B_{i-k} \right) n^{2l+1-i} = \\ & \sum_{i=0}^l \left(\frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{i} B_{l+i+1}}{l+i+1} \sum_{m=0}^{l-i} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-i}{m}}{l+m+1} \right) n^{2l+1-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=l+1}^{2l} \left(\sum_{k=0}^l \frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{m=\max(0, i-k-l)}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m} \binom{l+m+1}{i-k}}{l+m+1} B_{i-k} \right) n^{2l+1-i} \end{aligned}$$

If we increase index i in the above expression by $l+1$ then $P_2(n)$ is:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=l+1}^{2l+1} \left(\frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{i-l-1} B_i}{i} \sum_{m=0}^{2l+1-i} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{2l+1-i}{m}}{l+m+1} \right) n^{3l+2-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=2l+2}^{3l+1} \left(\sum_{k=0}^l \frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{m=\max(0, i-k-2l-1)}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m} \binom{l+m+1}{i-k-l-1}}{l+m+1} B_{i-k-l-1} \right) n^{3l+2-i} \end{aligned}$$

On three-dimensional expansions of the polynomial function $f(n) = n^m$

Our entry expression is equal to $P_1(n) + P_2(n)$ in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \frac{\binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k}{k+l+1} n^{3l+2} + \sum_{i=l+1}^{3l+1} B_i \sum_{k=i-l}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k \frac{\binom{k+l+1}{i}}{k+l+1} n^{3l+2-i} \right) + \\ & \sum_{i=l+1}^{2l+1} \left(\frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{i-l-1} B_i}{i} \sum_{m=0}^{2l+1-i} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{2l+1-i}{m}}{l+m+1} \right) n^{3l+2-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=2l+2}^{3l+1} \left(\sum_{k=0}^l \frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{m=\max(0, i-k-2l-1)}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m} \binom{l+m+1}{i-k-l-1}}{l+m+1} B_{i-k-l-1} \right) n^{3l+2-i}. \end{aligned}$$

After transformation of the above expression, the final formula for $\sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^l k^l (n-j-k)^l$ is :

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}} \sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \frac{\binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k}{k+l+1} n^{3l+2} + \\ & \sum_{i=l+1}^{2l+1} \left(\frac{1}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}} B_i \sum_{k=i-l}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k \frac{\binom{k+l+1}{i}}{k+l+1} \right) n^{3l+2-i} + \\ & \left(\frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{i-l-1} B_i}{i} \sum_{m=0}^{2l+1-i} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{2l+1-i}{m}}{l+m+1} \right) n^{3l+2-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=2l+2}^{3l+1} \left(\frac{1}{(2l+1) \binom{2l}{l}} B_i \sum_{k=i-l}^{2l+1} \binom{2l+1}{k} (-1)^k \frac{\binom{k+l+1}{i}}{k+l+1} \right) n^{3l+2-i} + \\ & \left(\sum_{k=0}^l \frac{2(-1)^l \binom{l}{k} B_{l+k+1}}{l+k+1} \sum_{m=\max(0, i-k-2l-1)}^{l-k} \frac{(-1)^m \binom{l-k}{m} \binom{l+m+1}{i-k-l-1}}{l+m+1} B_{i-k-l-1} \right) n^{3l+2-i} \end{aligned}$$

Let's mark the above formula as (7) .

On the base on formula (7) we can easy proof property **4.1**. The expression

$C_{l,l}(n) \sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^l k^l (n-j-k)^l$ must have coefficient 1 for the polynomial n^{3l+2} . This is satisfied

only when:

$$C_{l,l}(n) = C_{l,l,0} = (2l+1) \binom{2l}{l} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{2l+1} \frac{\binom{2l+1}{k}}{k+l+1} (-1)^k \right)^{-1}.$$

The proof of property 4.2

First, we need to define more precisely what n^t units are in $\sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^l k^l (n-j-k)^l$. Note that if

l is even, then only units with even powers can occur in this sum expression. In this case, the unit n^{3l+2} obviously has an even power. If we take the second item of the sum (7) then the unit n^{3l+2-i} is multiplied by B_i . The power of a unit is odd only if i is odd. Bernoulli numbers B_i are equal to 0 for i odd and $i > 1$.

This means that the coefficients for units with odd powers are also 0. Given the third item of the sum (7), we have 2 expression. In the first one, n^{3l+2-i} is multiplied by B_i , which is equal to 0 for i odd. The second is multiplied both by B_{l+k+1} and $B_{i-(k+l+1)}$. In this case, one of the numbers $B_{l+k+1}, B_{i-(k+l+1)}$ must be equal to 0 for i odd. This is because one of the indices $l+k+1, i-(k+l+1)$ must be both odd and > 1 . In this way, we have proved that for l even, in $\sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^l k^l (n-j-k)^l$ only units with an even power can exist.

Now consider when l is odd. In this case, the unit n^{3l+2} obviously has an odd power. On the other hand, the unit n^{3l+2-i} has an even power only if i is odd. If we take the second element in formula (7) again, the coefficients for units with even powers are equal to 0, because $B_i = 0$ for odd i and $i > 1$. Considering again the third position in (7), we have already noticed that if i is odd, then both B_i and one of the numbers $B_{l+k+1}, B_{i-(k+l+1)}$ must be equal to 0. In the final result, we have shown that when l is odd, only units with odd powers can be in $\sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^l k^l (n-j-k)^l$. Based on the

above considerations, we can represent the sum in question as follows:

$$\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} j^l k^l (n-j-k)^l = \begin{cases} a_{3l+2} n^{3l+2} + a_{2l} n^{2l} + a_{2l-2} n^{2l-2} + \dots + a_2 n^2 & \text{for } l \text{ even} \\ a_{3l+2} n^{3l+2} + a_{2l+1} n^{2l+1} + a_{2l-1} n^{2l-1} + \dots + a_1 n & \text{for } l \text{ odd} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

This, if we take 2 different units occurred in the sum under consideration, the difference between their powers can't be less than 2. In points 3.4.1 - 3.4.3, the method for finding the 3-D expansion of n^5, n^8 and n^{11} has been presented. We can also apply this method to any polynomial n^{3l+2} . In particular, we need to predict the exact form of the successive polynomial coefficients $C_{l,i}(n)$, starting with the highest possible index i and decreasing it by 1. Recall that $C_{l,i}(n)$ is a polynomial of degree at most 2 for $i \geq 1$. This factor is multiplied in 3-D expansion by $\sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^i k^i (n-j-k)^i$.

So that, a given $C_{l,i}(n)$ must be of the form to eliminate some consecutive units n^t occurring in $\sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^l k^l (n-j-k)^l$ or which appeared in some $C_{l,v}(n) \sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^v k^v (n-j-k)^v$ for $i < v < l$. The number of units we can eliminate with the factor $C_{l,i}(n)$ depends on the exact form of this factor. For example, if $C_{l,i}(n) = C_{l,i,0}$ then we can eliminate the unit n^{3i+2} , while if $C_{l,i}(n) = C_{l,i,2} n^2 + C_{l,i,1} n$ then we can remove 2 units i.e. n^{3i+4} and n^{3i+3} . On the other hand, a given polynomial coefficient $C_{l,i}(n)$ cannot introduce a new unit that does not appear in $C_{l,v}(n) \sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^v k^v (n-j-k)^v$ for $i < v \leq l$. Otherwise, we couldn't later eliminate such a unit

by the coefficients $C_{l,v}(n)$ for $v < i$. For this reason, $C_{l,i}(n)$ cannot contain units for which the difference between their powers is less than 2.

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This means exactly that the coefficient can't be: $C_{l,i,2}n^2 + C_{l,i,1}n + C_{l,i,0}$, $C_{l,i,2}n^2 + C_{l,i,1}n$ and $C_{l,i,1}n + C_{l,i,0}$. The only exception to this rule is the case of $C_{l,1}(n)$. The form $C_{l,1,1}n + C_{l,1,0}$ is then allowed. When $C_{l,1}(n)$ has this form, it means that we eliminate the unit n^6 and l is even. At the same time, we introduce a new unit n^5 , which is not present in $C_{l,v}(n) \sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^v k^v (n-j-k)^v$

for $1 < v \leq l$. However, this isn't a problem, because in the next step we can eliminate n^5 with the coefficient $C_{l,0}(n)$. As defined in 3.2. this coefficient is a degree 3 polynomial which is multiplied by $\frac{n^2+3n}{2}$ during 3-D expansion.

In general, we must note that if at least one unit with a equal to or less than 5 is to be eliminated, the coefficient $C_{l,1,0}$ must always be non-zero and $C_{l,0}(n)$ must be a 3rd degree polynomial. To proof it, let's consider 2 cases: l is even and l is odd.

When l is even, we need to eliminate the units n^4 and or n^2 . When $C_{l,1,0} = 0$ then we could only do it with $C_{l,0}(n)$. If we eliminate n^4 then $C_{l,0}(n)$ must be $C_{l,0,2}n^2 + C_{l,0,1}n + C_{l,0,0}$. When multiplied by $\frac{n^2+3n}{2}$ we get a degree 4 polynomial containing the units n^4, n^3, n^2, n^1 . We would then have to eliminate 4 units using only 3 parameters $C_{l,0,2}, C_{l,0,1}, C_{l,0,0}$. In other words, we would have to satisfy 4 conditions (a linear equation for each unit), with fewer unknown parameters. It's very easy to prove (given the matrix of this system of equations), that it would be impossible in this case. In the end, we wouldn't be able to create any 3-D expansion. Similarly, when we eliminate only n^2 , then $C_{l,0}(n)$ would have to be $C_{l,0,0}$. When multiplied by $\frac{n^2+3n}{2}$, we get a degree 2 polynomial containing n^2, n units. In this situation, we would have to eliminate 2 units with only 1 parameter $C_{l,0,0}$. Of course we couldn't do that.

If we consider the second case i.e. l is odd, we need to eliminate the units n^5 and or n^3 and or n . If we eliminate n^5 and $C_{l,1,0} = 0$ then $C_{l,0}(n)$ must be a degree 3 polynomial. When multiplied by $\frac{n^2+3n}{2}$, we get a degree 5 polynomial with the units n^5, n^4, n^3, n^2, n . We would then have to eliminate 5 units with only 4 parameters $C_{l,0,3}, C_{l,0,2}, C_{l,0,1}, C_{l,0,0}$. In a similar way, we can prove that if we eliminate only n^3 or n then $C_{l,1,0}$ cannot be equal to 0 and $C_{l,0}(n)$ must be a polynomial third degree.

Given the complexity of formula (7), we can't be absolutely sure without any mathematical proof that all coefficients a_t in formula (8) are non-zero. Still, if any a_t is equal to zero, this fact is irrelevant to the existence of a potential 3-D expansion. To prove this, consider 2 cases: $t > 5$ and $t \leq 5$. Also suppose our present polynomial elimination coefficient is $C_{l,i}(n)$. In the first case, if $a_t = 0$ then it is possible that n^t occurs in some $C_{l,v}(n) \sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^v k^v (n-j-k)^v$ for $i < v < l$.

Even if it isn't true, we have no problem here, because in this situation the corresponding coefficient in $C_{l,i}(n)$ will be equal to 0.

In the second case ($t \leq 5$), it is possible that n^t occurs in some $C_{l,v}(n) \sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} j^v k^v (n-j-k)^v$

for $1 < v < l$. If it isn't true, then we have no problem either, because it will be taken into account in the conditions for the coefficients that appear in both expressions: $C_{l,1}(n) \sum_{0 < j+k \leq n} jk(n-j-k)$

and $C_{l,0}(n) \frac{n^2+3n}{2}$. These factors are: $C_{l,1,0}, C_{l,0,3}, C_{l,0,2}, C_{l,0,1}, C_{l,0,0}$.

5.Expected forms of 3-D expansions for the functions $f(n) = n^{14}$, $f(n) = n^{17}$ and $f(n) = n^{20}$

Based on the method and properties presented in points 3.4, 4 we can predict what should be the general form of the 3-D expansion for a given function $f(n) = n^{3l+2}$. In this section we present these forms for the functions $f(n) = n^{14}$, $f(n) = n^{17}$ and $f(n) = n^{20}$.

5.1. The case of $f(n) = n^{14}$

In this case $l = 4$. We can represent $\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} j^4 k^4 (n-j-k)^4$ in the following polynomial form:

$$\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} j^4 k^4 (n-j-k)^4 = a_{14} n^{14} + a_8 n^8 + a_6 n^6 + a_4 n^4 + a_2 n^2$$

Given the polynomial form of the sum under consideration, the coefficient $C_{4,3}(n)$ must by definition be equal to 0. The first unit which we should eliminate is n^8 , so the coefficient $C_{4,2}(n)$ must be equal to $C_{4,2,0}$. The second is n^6 , so the coefficient $C_{4,1}(n)$ must be $C_{4,1,1}n + C_{4,1,0}$. The next 2 units n^4 and n^2 can only be eliminated by the coefficient $C_{4,0}(n)$, which is a 3rd degree polynomial of the form $C_{4,0,3}n^3 + C_{4,0,2}n^2 + C_{4,0,1}n + C_{4,0,0}$. With $C_{4,0}(n)$ we will also eliminate the n^5 unit, that came up earlier due to $C_{4,1}(n)$.

Thus, we can represent the general form of 3-D expansion as follows:

$$n^{14} = \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} \left(C_{4,4,0} j^4 k^4 (n-j-k)^4 + C_{4,2,0} j^2 k^2 (n-j-k)^2 + (C_{4,1,1}n + C_{4,1,0})jk(n-j-k) \right) + C_{4,0,3}n^3 + C_{4,0,2}n^2 + C_{4,0,1}n + C_{4,0,0}$$

If we want to find the exact 3-D expansion of n^{14} , we can use the system of linear equations method. Then we get a system of 8 equations with 8 unknowns. The numbers of equations and unknowns result from the fact that after appropriate transformations we have 8 units ($n^{14}, n^8, n^6, n^5, n^4, n^3, n^2, n^1$) from their factors depending on 8 unknown expansion factors ($C_{4,4,0}, C_{4,2,0}, C_{4,1,1}, C_{4,1,0}, C_{4,0,3}, C_{4,0,2}, C_{4,0,1}, C_{4,0,0}$).

5.2. The case of $f(n) = n^{17}$

In this case $l = 5$. The sum in question can be presented in the following polynomial form:

$$\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} j^5 k^5 (n-j-k)^5 = a_{17} n^{17} + a_{11} n^{11} + a_9 n^9 + a_7 n^7 + a_5 n^5 + a_3 n^3 + a_1 n$$

Given the polynomial form of the sum under consideration, the coefficient $C_{5,4}(n)$ must by definition be equal to 0.

The first unit we should eliminate is n^{11} , so the coefficient $C_{5,3}(n)$ must be $C_{5,3,0}$. The second is n^9 , so the factor $C_{5,2}(n)$ must be $C_{5,2,1}n$.

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The next 2 units n^7, n^5 can only be eliminated by the factor $C_{5,1}(n)$, which must be $C_{5,1,2}n^2 + C_{5,1,0}$. The last 2 units n^3, n will be eliminated by $C_{5,0}(n)$ of the form $C_{5,0,3}n^3 + C_{5,0,2}n^2 + C_{5,0,1}n + C_{5,0,0}$. Thus, we can represent the general form of 3-D expansion as:

$$n^{17} = \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} \left(\begin{aligned} &C_{5,5,0}j^5k^5(n-j-k)^5 + C_{5,3,0}j^3k^3(n-j-k)^3 + C_{5,2,1}nj^2k^2(n-j-k)^2 \\ &+ (C_{5,1,2}n^2 + C_{5,1,0})jk(n-j-k) + C_{5,0,3}n^3 + C_{5,0,2}n^2 + C_{5,0,1}n + C_{5,0,0} \end{aligned} \right)$$

As in the previous case, we can find the exact 3-D expansion of n^{17} using the system of linear equations method. Then we get a system of 9 equations with 9 unknowns, because after appropriate transformations we have 9 units ($n^{17}, n^{11}, n^9, n^7, n^5, n^4, n^3, n^2, n^1$) whose coefficients depended on the 9 searched expansion parameters ($C_{5,5,0}, C_{5,3,0}, C_{5,2,1}, C_{5,1,2}, C_{5,1,0}, C_{5,0,3}, C_{5,0,2}, C_{5,0,1}, C_{5,0,0}$).

5.3. The case of $f(n) = n^{20}$

In this case $l = 6$. The sum in question can be presented in the following polynomial form:

$$\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} j^6k^6(n-j-k)^6 = a_{20}n^{20} + a_{12}n^{12} + a_{10}n^{10} + a_8n^8 + a_6n^6 + a_4n^4 + a_2n^2$$

Given the formula above, the coefficients $C_{6,5}(n)$ and $C_{6,4}(n)$ must by definition be equal to 0. The first unit we should eliminate is n^{12} , so that the coefficient $C_{6,3}(n)$ must be in the form $C_{6,3,1}n$. The next 2 units are n^{10} and n^8 , so the coefficient $C_{6,2}(n)$ must be $C_{6,2,2}n^2 + C_{6,2,0}$. The next unit is n^6 and can only be eliminated by the factor $C_{6,1}(n)$, which must be $C_{6,1,1}n + C_{6,1,0}$. The last 2 units n^4 and n^2 will be eliminated by $C_{6,0}(n)$ in the form of $C_{6,0,3}n^3 + C_{6,0,2}n^2 + C_{6,0,1}n + C_{6,0,0}$.

With $C_{6,0}(n)$ we will also eliminate n^5 which came up earlier due to $C_{6,1}(n)$. Thus, we can represent the general form of 3-D expansion as:

$$n^{20} = \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} \left(\begin{aligned} &C_{6,6,0}j^6k^6(n-j-k)^6 + C_{6,3,1}nj^3k^3(n-j-k)^3 \\ &+ (C_{6,2,2}n^2 + C_{6,2,0})j^2k^2(n-j-k)^2 \\ &+ (C_{6,1,1}n + C_{6,1,0})jk(n-j-k) + C_{6,0,3}n^3 + C_{6,0,2}n^2 + C_{6,0,1}n + C_{6,0,0} \end{aligned} \right)$$

As in the previous cases, we can find the exact 3-D expansion of n^{20} using the system of linear equations method. Then we will get a system of 10 equations with the same number of unknowns, because after appropriate transformations we have 10 units ($n^{20}, n^{12}, n^{10}, n^8, n^6, n^5, n^4, n^3, n^2, n^1$), where their coefficients depend on the 10 sought expansion coefficients ($C_{6,6,0}, C_{6,3,1}, C_{6,2,2}, C_{6,2,0}, C_{6,1,1}, C_{6,1,0}, C_{6,0,3}, C_{6,0,2}, C_{6,0,1}, C_{6,0,0}$).

6. Summary and Questions

In this article, we presented the definition, examples and properties of three-dimensional expansions of a polynomial function in the form $f(n) = n^{3l+2}$, where l natural and $l \geq 1$. (point 3). These expansions have the form:

$$n^{3l+2} = \sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} \sum_{i=0}^l C_{l,i}(n) j^i k^i (n-j-k)^i$$

where $\{C_{l,l}(n), C_{l,l-1}(n), \dots, C_{l,1}(n), C_{l,0}(n)\}$ are the expansion coefficients in a polynomial of degree up to 3 (definition 3.2 and properties 4.1, 4.2).

We presented also the method of obtaining exact expansions for the lowest 3 powers i.e. when $l = 1, 2, 3$ (point 3.4). However, this method requires knowing the exact polynomial form of the expression $\sum_{\substack{j,k: \\ 0 < j+k \leq n}} j^i k^i (n-j-k)^i$ for $1 \leq i \leq l$ before using it.

Point 4 presents the basic properties of 3-D expansions. These properties make it possible to predict the exact form of the coefficients $C_{l,i}(n)$ in a given expansion, without calculating their exact values. Based on this, point 5 shows the expected form of 3-D expansions for $f(n) = n^{14}$, $f(n) = n^{17}$ and $f(n) = n^{20}$.

From the content presented in this article, it follows that for every $l \geq 1$ there is a 3-D expansion of n^{3l+2} according to definition 3.2. At the same time, it is quite easy to prove that there are no 2 different 3-D expansions for a given polynomial function. The following are questions related to 3-D expansions that came up while working on this article:

Question 1.

Is there an compact algorithm that can calculate the coefficients $C_{l,i}(n)$ for a given function $f(n) = n^{3l+2}$?

Question 2.

The exact expansions of n^5, n^8 and n^{11} show that $C_{1,0}(3) = 0$, $C_{2,0}(3) = 0$ and $C_{3,0}(3) = 0$. Is it true that for every $f(n) = n^{3l+2}$ $C_{l,0}(3) = 0$ is true ?

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